

LINEAR RELATIONS FOR OVERPARTITIONS INTO ODD PARTS

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Received: 9/1/25, Accepted: 4/24/26, Published: 5/1/26

Abstract

Let $\bar{p}_o(n)$ denote the number of overpartitions of n into odd parts. The partition function $\bar{p}_o(n)$ has been the subject of numerous recent studies, in which many explicit Ramanujan-like congruences have been discovered. In this paper, we provide three linear recurrence relations for $\bar{p}_o(n)$. Several connections with partitions into parts not congruent to 2 (mod 4), overpartitions, and partitions into distinct parts are presented in this context.

1. Introduction

A *partition* of a non-negative integer n is defined as a finite non-increasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is n . For example, there are seven partitions of 5:

$$5, 4 + 1, 3 + 2, 3 + 1 + 1, 2 + 2 + 1, 2 + 1 + 1 + 1, 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1.$$

We denote the number of partitions of n by $p(n)$. The generating function of $p(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}},$$

where

$$(a; q)_n = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } n = 0, \\ \prod_{k=1}^n (1 - aq^{k-1}), & \text{for } n > 0 \end{cases}$$

is the q -shifted factorial,

$$(a; q)_\infty = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a; q)_n, \quad |q| < 1.$$

An *overpartition* of a non-negative integer n is a partition of n in which the first occurrence of parts of each size may be overlined. For example, there are eight overpartitions of the integer 3:

$$3, \bar{3}, 2 + 1, \bar{2} + 1, 2 + \bar{1}, \bar{2} + \bar{1}, 1 + 1 + 1, \bar{1} + 1 + 1.$$

We denote the number of overpartitions of n by $\bar{p}(n)$. The generating function of $\bar{p}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n)q^n = \frac{(-q; q)_\infty}{(q; q)_\infty}. \tag{1.1}$$

For more details on overpartitions, see [5], [9], [10], and [13].

Now consider that n has been overpartitioned into odd parts. We denote the number of such partitions by $\bar{p}_o(n)$. The series-product identity due to Lebesgue [12] represents the generating function of $\bar{p}_o(n)$:

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1; q)_j q^{j(j+1)/2}}{(q; q)_j} = \frac{(-q; q^2)_\infty}{(q; q^2)_\infty}.$$

For more details on overpartitions into odd parts, see [3] and [11].

Euler [1] presented the following recurrence relation for the partition function $p(n)$ involving pentagonal numbers:

$$\begin{aligned} p(n) - p(n - 1) - p(n - 2) + p(n - 5) + p(n - 7) - p(n - 12) - p(n - 15) \\ + \dots + (-1)^k p(n - k(3k - 1)/2) + (-1)^k p(n - k(3k + 1)/2) + \dots \\ = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n = 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Further, in 1973, Ewell [7] gave the following recurrence relation for the partition function $p(n)$:

$$\begin{aligned} p(n) - p(n - 1) - p(n - 3) + p(n - 6) + p(n - 10) - p(n - 15) - p(n - 21) \\ + \dots + (-1)^{\lceil j/2 \rceil} p(n - j(j + 1)/2) + (-1)^{\lceil j/2 \rceil} p(n - j(j + 1)/2) + \dots \\ = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ p_d(n) & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where $p_d(n)$ denotes the number of partitions of n into distinct parts. Choliy, Kolitsch, and Sills [4] also gave two Euler-type recurrences for $p(n)$, stated below:

$$p(n) - p(n - 1) - p(n - 2) + p(n - 4) + p(n - 8) - p(n - 9) - p(n - 18) + \dots \\ \dots + (-1)^j p(n - j^2) + (-1)^j p(n - 2j^2) + \dots = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \\ p_{do}(n) & \text{if } n \text{ is even,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$p(n) - 2p(n - 1) + 2p(n - 4) - \dots + (-1)^j 2p(n - j^2) + \dots = (-1)^i p_{do}(n),$$

where $p_{do}(n)$ denotes the number of partitions of n into distinct odd parts. In [14], Merca gave two linear recurrence relations for the partition function $p(n)$ using consequences of bisections of the pentagonal number theorem. He also established a relation showing that the partition functions $p(n)$ and $p_{do}(n)$ have the same parity. One of the main results is given below:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p\left(n - \frac{G_k}{2}\right) - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p\left(\frac{n}{2} - \frac{k(k+1)}{8}\right) = 0,$$

with $p(x) = 0$ when x is a negative integer and G_k represents generalized pentagonal numbers given as:

$$G_k = \frac{1}{2} [k/2] (3[k/2] + (-1)^k).$$

Recently, da Silva and Sakai [6] derived several recurrence relations for $p(n)$, $p_{do}(n)$, $\bar{p}(n)$, the partition function with odd parts $p_o(n)$, and p_m^c , the partition function of n with parts congruent to $\pm c$ modulo m , by invoking classical identities and generating function manipulations.

Merca [15] also provided two recurrence relations for the function $\text{ped}(n)$, where $\text{ped}(n)$ denotes the number of partitions of n with distinct even parts and unrestricted odd parts. Its generating function is

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{ped}(n)q^n = \frac{(q^4; q^4)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}}.$$

The two recurrence relations for $\text{ped}(n)$ due to Merca are the following.

Theorem 1 ([15]). *For $n \geq 0$,*

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil j/2 \rceil} \text{ped}(n - j(j+1)/2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n = k(k+1), \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2 ([15]). *For $n \geq 0$,*

$$\sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^j \text{ped}(n - 2j^2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n = k(k+1)/2, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Motivated by the above works, we establish three recurrence relations for $\bar{p}_o(n)$. The following recurrence relation is analogous to Euler’s recurrence for $p(n)$, as well as to the recurrences for $\text{ped}(n)$ and $\text{pod}(n)$.

Theorem 3. *For any integer $n \geq 0$,*

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k \bar{p}_o\left(n - \frac{k(3k+1)}{2}\right) = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\lceil m/2 \rceil}, & \text{if } n = \frac{m(3m+1)}{2}, m \in \mathbb{Z}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In the following, we state the recurrence relations for $\bar{p}_o(n)$ that involve the triangular numbers, $k(k+1)/2$, $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, and the perfect square numbers, respectively.

Theorem 4. *For any integer $n \geq 0$,*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil k/2 \rceil} \bar{p}_o\left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2}\right) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n = \frac{m(m+1)}{2}, m \in \mathbb{N}_0, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 5. *For any integer $n \geq 0$,*

$$\bar{p}_o(n) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \bar{p}_o(n - 2k^2) = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{if } n = m^2, m \in \mathbb{N}, \\ 1, & \text{if } n = 0, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

If n is small then it is relatively easy to evaluate $\bar{p}_o(n)$, namely

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{p}_o(0) &= 1, \\ \bar{p}_o(1) &= 2, \\ \bar{p}_o(2) &= 2\bar{p}_o(0) = 2, \\ \bar{p}_o(3) &= 2\bar{p}_o(1) = 4, \\ \bar{p}_o(4) &= 2 + 2\bar{p}_o(2) = 6, \\ \bar{p}_o(5) &= 2\bar{p}_o(3) = 8, \\ \bar{p}_o(6) &= 2\bar{p}_o(4) = 12, \\ \bar{p}_o(7) &= 2\bar{p}_o(5) = 16, \\ \bar{p}_o(8) &= 2(\bar{p}_o(6) - \bar{p}_o(0)) = 22, \\ \bar{p}_o(9) &= 2 + 2(\bar{p}_o(7) - \bar{p}_o(1)) = 30, \\ \bar{p}_o(10) &= 2\bar{p}_o(8) - \bar{p}_o(2) = 40. \end{aligned}$$

We prove Theorems 3 – 5 in Section 2 and connections with $p_o(n)$, and other partition functions are established in Section 3.

2. Proofs of Theorems 3 – 5

Jacobi’s triple product identity can be stated in terms of Ramanujan’s theta function [2, p. 34] as follows:

$$(-a; ab)_\infty (-b; ab)_\infty (ab; ab)_\infty = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a^{n(n+1)/2} b^{n(n-1)/2}. \tag{2.1}$$

Proof of Theorem 3. Replacing a by $-q^2$ and b by $-q$ in (2.1), we get

$$(q; q^3)_\infty (q^2; q^3)_\infty (q^3; q^3)_\infty = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)/2}, \tag{2.2}$$

which is Euler’s pentagonal number theorem. The above identity can be rewritten as

$$(-q; -q^3)_\infty (q^2; -q^3)_\infty (-q^3; -q^3)_\infty = \frac{(-q; q^2)_\infty}{(q; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)/2}. \tag{2.3}$$

Replacing a by $-q^2$ and b by q in (2.1), we derive

$$(-q; -q^3)_\infty (q^2; -q^3)_\infty (-q^3; -q^3)_\infty = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil n/2 \rceil} q^{n(3n+1)/2}. \tag{2.4}$$

In view of (2.3) and (2.4), we arrive at

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil n/2 \rceil} q^{n(3n+1)/2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n) q^n \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)/2}. \tag{2.5}$$

Theorem 3 follows from the above identity. □

Proof of Theorem 4. By (2.1), with replacing a by $-q^3$ and b by $-q$, we obtain

$$(q; q^4)_\infty (q^3; q^4)_\infty (q^4; q^4)_\infty = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{2n^2+n}.$$

The above identity can be rewritten as

$$(-q; q^2)_\infty (q^4; q^4)_\infty = \frac{(-q; q^2)_\infty}{(q; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil n/2 \rceil} q^{n(n+1)/2}. \tag{2.6}$$

Replacing a by q^3 and b by q in (2.1), we derive the identities

$$(-q; q^4)_\infty (-q^3; q^4)_\infty (q^4; q^4)_\infty = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2}. \tag{2.7}$$

$$\frac{(q^2; q^2)_\infty^2}{(q; q)_\infty} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty q^{n(n+1)/2}. \tag{2.8}$$

By (2.6) and (2.7), we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^\infty q^{n(n+1)/2} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \bar{p}_o(n) q^n \sum_{n=0}^\infty (-1)^{\lceil n/2 \rceil} q^{n(n+1)/2}.$$

Theorem 4 follows from the last identity. □

Proof of Theorem 5. Replacing a and b by $-q^2$ in (2.1), we obtain

$$(q^2; q^4)_\infty (q^2; q^4)_\infty (q^4; q^4)_\infty = \sum_{n=-\infty}^\infty (-1)^n q^{2n^2}.$$

Rewriting the above equation, we see that

$$(-q; q^2)_\infty (-q; q^2)_\infty (q^2; q^2)_\infty = \frac{(-q; q^2)_\infty}{(q; q^2)_\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^\infty (-1)^n q^{2n^2}. \tag{2.9}$$

By replacing a and b by q in (2.1), we obtain

$$(-q; q^2)_\infty^2 (q^2; q^2)_\infty = \sum_{n=-\infty}^\infty q^{n^2}, \tag{2.10}$$

From (2.9) and (2.10), we have

$$\sum_{n=-\infty}^\infty q^{n^2} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \bar{p}_o(n) q^n \sum_{n=-\infty}^\infty (-1)^n q^{2n^2}.$$

Equating the coefficient of q^n on both sides of the above equation, we arrive at Theorem 5. □

3. Relation Connecting $\bar{p}_o(n)$ with Other Partition Functions

Let $\text{pod}(n)$ denote the number of partitions of n wherein odd parts are distinct and even parts are unrestricted. The generating function for $\text{pod}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^\infty \text{pod}(n) q^n = \frac{(-q; q^2)_\infty}{(q^2; q^2)_\infty}. \tag{3.1}$$

We shall prove that $\bar{p}_o(n)$ can be expressed in terms of $\text{pod}(n)$.

Theorem 6. For any integer $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}_o(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \text{pod} \left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2} \right).$$

Proof. From (3.1), we have

$$\frac{(-q; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q; q^2)_{\infty}} = (q^2; q^2)_{\infty} (-q; q)_{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}(n) q^n.$$

By (2.8), we deduce that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n) q^n = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \text{pod}(n) q^n \right) \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(n+1)/2} \right).$$

The proof follows from the last identity. □

The parity of $\bar{p}_o(n)$ and Theorem 6 allows us to derive the following congruence.

Corollary 1. For any integer $n > 0$,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \text{pod} \left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

The partition functions $p(n)$ and $\bar{p}_o(n)$ can be related as follows.

Theorem 7. For any integer $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}_o(n) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil k/2 \rceil} p \left(n - \frac{k(3k+1)}{2} \right).$$

Proof. From (2.2), we have

$$\frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}} = \left[\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)/2} \right]^{-1}.$$

From (2.5), we see that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n) q^n = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n) q^n \right) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil n/2 \rceil} q^{n(3n+1)/2} \right).$$

The proof follows from the above identity. □

Corollary 2. For any integer $n > 0$,

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} p \left(n - \frac{k(3k+1)}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

Proof. It easily follows from the Theorem 7 and the parity of $\bar{p}_o(n)$. □

Theorem 8. For any integer $n \geq 0$,

$$\bar{p}_o(n) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k \bar{p}(n - 2k^2).$$

Proof. Considering the generating function of $\bar{p}_o(n)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n &= (-q; q)_{\infty}(-q; q^2)_{\infty} \\ &= \frac{(-q; q)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}}(-q; q^2)_{\infty}(q; q)_{\infty}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

Using Equations (2.9) and (1.1), we see that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n)q^n \right) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{2n^2} \right).$$

The proof follows from the final equation. □

The Equation (3.3) below appears in Theorem 2.12 of [11], while (3.4) is due to Hemanthkumar and Chandankumar [8]:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(2n + 1)q^n = 2 \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}(q^8; q^8)_{\infty}^2}{(q; q)_{\infty}^2 (q^4; q^4)_{\infty}} \tag{3.3}$$

and

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(2n)q^n = \frac{(q^4; q^4)_{\infty}^5}{(q; q)_{\infty}^2 (q^2; q^2)_{\infty} (q^8; q^8)_{\infty}^2}. \tag{3.4}$$

Theorem 9. For any non-negative integer n ,

$$\bar{p}_o(2n + 1) = 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n - 2k(k + 1)).$$

Proof. Rearranging (3.3), using the generating function of $\bar{p}(n)$ and (2.8), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(2n + 1)q^n &= 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n)q^n \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{\frac{4n(n+1)}{2}}, \\ &= 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n - 2k(k + 1)) \right) q^n. \end{aligned}$$

Equating the coefficient of q^n on both sides of the last equation, we arrive at the result. □

Theorem 10. *For any non-negative integer n ,*

$$\bar{p}_o(2n) = \bar{p}(n) + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n - 2k^2).$$

Proof. Rearranging Equations (3.4) and (1.1), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(2n)q^n = \frac{(q^4; q^4)_{\infty}^5}{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2 (q^8; q^8)_{\infty}^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n)q^n.$$

Invoking (2.10), we get

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(2n)q^n = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{2n^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}(n)q^n.$$

Equating the coefficient of q^n on both sides of the above equation completes the proof. \square

Let $P_2(n)$ denote the partition function of n with parts not congruent to 2 (mod 4). The generating function of $P_2(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_2(n)q^n = \frac{(q^2; q^4)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}}.$$

Let $\bar{q}(n)$ denote the bipartition function of n into distinct parts. The generating function for $\bar{q}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{q}(n)q^n = (-q; q)_{\infty}^2.$$

Theorem 11. *For any positive integer n ,*

$$\bar{p}_o(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} P_2\left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2}\right).$$

Proof. Considering the generating function of $\bar{p}_o(n)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n &= \frac{(-q; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} \\ &= \frac{(q^2; q^4)_{\infty}}{(q; q)_{\infty}} \frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2}{(q; q)_{\infty}}. \end{aligned}$$

Invoking (2.8) in the above equation, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_2(n)q^n \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} P_2 \left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2} \right) \right) q^n. \end{aligned}$$

Equating the coefficient of q^n on both sides of the above equation completes the proof. \square

The parity of $\bar{p}_o(n)$ and Theorem 11 allow us to derive the following congruence.

Corollary 3. *For any integer $n > 0$,*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} P_2 \left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

The following result is a relation connecting the partition functions $\bar{q}(n)$ and $p(n)$.

Theorem 12. *For any positive integer n ,*

$$\bar{q}(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p \left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2} \right).$$

Proof. Consider the generating function of $\bar{p}_o(n)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n &= (-q; q^2)_{\infty} (-q; q)_{\infty} \\ &= \frac{(-q; q^2)_{\infty}}{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} \left(\frac{(q^2; q^2)_{\infty}^2}{(q; q)_{\infty}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}} \times \frac{1}{(-q^2; q^2)_{\infty}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Rewriting the above equation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (-q^2; q^2)_{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{q}(n)q^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p \left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2} \right) \right) q^n. \end{aligned}$$

Equating the coefficient of q^n on each side of the previous equation completes the proof. \square

Let $p_d(n)$ denote the number of partitions of n into distinct parts. The number of partitions of n into distinct odd parts is denoted by $p_{do}(n)$. The generating functions for $p_d(n)$ and $p_{do}(n)$ are given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_d(n)q^n = (-q; q)_{\infty}$$

and

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_{do}(n)q^n = (-q; q^2)_{\infty}.$$

It is easy to see that

$$\bar{p}_o(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n p_d(k)p_{do}(n - k).$$

Theorem 13. For any integer $n \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k \bar{p}_o\left(n - \frac{k(3k+1)}{2}\right) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k p_{do}(n - k(3k+1)).$$

Proof. Rewriting (3.2), we get

$$(-q; q^2)_{\infty}(-q; q)_{\infty}(q; q)_{\infty} = (-q; q^2)_{\infty}(q^2; q^2)_{\infty},$$

which implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n)q^n\right) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)/2}\right) &= \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_{do}(n)q^n\right) \\ &\times \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

□

By using Theorem 3 and Theorem 13, we obtain the following recurrence relation for $p_{do}(n)$.

Corollary 4. For any integer $n \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k p_{do}(n - k(3k+1)) = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\lceil m/2 \rceil}, & \text{if } n = \frac{m(3m+1)}{2}, m \in \mathbb{Z}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 14. For any integer $n \geq 0$,

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil k/2 \rceil} \bar{p}_o\left(n - \frac{k(k+1)}{2}\right) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k p_d(n - k(3k+1)).$$

Proof. Rewriting relation (3.2), we see that

$$(-q; q)_\infty (-q; q^2)_\infty (q; q^2)_\infty (q^4; q^4)_\infty = (-q; q)_\infty (q^2; q^2)_\infty,$$

which implies that

$$\left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \bar{p}_o(n) q^n \right) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^{\lceil n/2 \rceil} q^{n(n+1)/2} \right) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_d(n) q^n \right) \times \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n q^{n(3n+1)} \right),$$

where we have used (2.6). □

By using Theorem 4 and Theorem 14, we obtain the following recurrence relation for $p_d(n)$.

Corollary 5. *For any integer $n \geq 0$,*

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^k p_d(n - k(3k + 1)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n = \frac{m(m+1)}{2}, m \in \mathbb{N}_0, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

Acknowledgement. The authors would like to thank Dr. B. Hemanthkumar for the information about the article [15] and also for his valuable suggestions. The authors would also like to sincerely thank the anonymous reviewer for their meticulous and insightful feedback. The thoughtful comments and suggestions have significantly improved the quality and rigor of this work. The authors gratefully acknowledge the Managing Editor for his valuable grammatical suggestions that enhanced the clarity and readability of the manuscript.

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